

Flexible, Conducting Electrospun Pt Nanoislands@Carbon Nanofibers for Low-Temperature H₂ Gas Sensor Applications

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ABSTRACT

Self standing electrospun carbon nanofibers (CNFs) have a lot of applications due to their high surface area, controllable electronic conductivity and simplicity of preparation. Incorporation of catalytic, Platinum nanoparticles (Pt NPs), onto CNFs can enhance their electron transport properties. Herein, we report a two-step process for the successful development of highly flexible and conducting carbon nanofibers with surface anchored Platinum nanoislands (PtNI@CNFs) using a simple combination of electrospinning and electrochemical deposition. Surface morphology of the PtNI@CNFs was characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy and Atomic force microscopy. Homogeneous distribution of Pt NIs on the surface of CNFs were characterized by HRTEM. Thermal analysis of the material was analyzed using TGA. The coverage density of Pt NIs on the surface of CNFs could be controlled by varying the deposition time during electrochemical deposition. The electron transport properties of CNFs and PtNI@CNFs were studied using I-V measurements. Low temperature H₂ gas sensing properties of CNFs and PtNI@CNFs were analyzed.

Key words: Electrospinning, Electrochemical deposition, Carbon nanofibers, Pt NI@CNE, gas sensors

References:

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